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THE PLACE OF OPERA ART IN UZBEKISTAN

Ibragimova Sitora Sunnat kizi

teacher,

Uzbek National Music Art Institute named after Yunus Rajabi

***Abstract.** The article discusses the issues of Uzbek opera singers and their performing skills. Based on the analysis of their creativity. Expressive means in operas are identified, aimed at interpreting operas, educating the younger generation through images in operas, and also through art.*

***Keywords:** composer, opera, libretto, vocals, poppy, singer, aria.*

The art of singing, which is the most common part of the Uzbek national music culture, has been developing in our country for centuries. The art of singing has been connected with the life of almost all peoples since ancient times. It is known that traditional ritual folk songs were performed by singers and singers on the occasion of one or another ceremony, and they have reached us to this day.

By the 20th century, the art form of singing continued in its own genres with the introduction of vocal, academic singing directions from the 20s and 30s. At first, the work of a single composer was in the form of songs written for soloists, romances, then it developed and strengthened in major genres such as musical drama, opera, operetta, oratorio and cantata, mass and requiem. These made a great contribution to the development of Uzbek academic singing and vocal performance.

The rapid development of vocal art, that is, the opening of the Tashkent State Conservatory in 1936 on Uzbek soil, and the presence of the vocal department among the first departments in it, paved the way for the growth of the field. Teachers who worked in this department were S.Benyaminov, R.Kuchlikovalar, N.Hoshimov, R.Chepchirenko, N.Izrailyan, R.Yusupova, R.Laut, N.Goldman, A.Odilov, K.Mukhitdinov, N.Qoziev, S. Qabulova, S. Tsoi taught the students. Many of them are

representatives of the St. Petersburg and Moscow academic singing schools, and it can be said that this school in some sense taught Uzbek youth and helped them achieve great success on the world stage.

On the other hand, these teachers are at the same time practical performers of large theater stages, concert stages, i.e., they are also theoreticians who perfectly know the characteristics of sound. Teaching in a way that combines these two methods will definitely bring students great newness and skills. Currently, the students who received education from these teachers and continued their path are working in the Department of "Academic Singing and Opera Preparation" of the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan, and some of them at the same time in DAKT named after Alisher Navoi. People's artists of Uzbekistan A. Radjabov, I. Djalilov, N. Sultonov, Honored artists of Uzbekistan O. Aleksandrova, R. Gafarov, Sh. Gafurov, Honored cultural worker of Uzbekistan, professor M. Rizaeva, professor G. Mukhamedova, associate professor E. Tursunov, teachers Ya. Bagryanskaya, L. Saidmukhamedova, A. Bakirov, B. Matkarimova, D. Rakhmanovlar, Doctor of Arts, Professor M.Khamidova, laureates of the Republic and International Competitions as opera conductors S.Goipov, B.Khudaykulov, N.Pardaeva, S.Radjabov, opera directors Professor G.Mukhamedova, senior teacher U.Khaydarov, R.Azizova possible Their joint work in the department has a very important place in the education of young opera singers, preserving traditions and vocal schools, and we can see the results of their fruitful creativity on the Uzbek and world stages, in the activities of opera theaters, concerts and tours, competitions and festivals. Among those who studied at the department and are currently studying: Zulfiya State Prize winners Sh.Yakubjonova and G.Abdulkhamidova, "Nihol" State Prize winners H.Komilov, A.Piyazov, F.Shamsieva, H.Imomnazarova, A.Jumanyozov, R.Shekhnazarov, Sh. Artikov, Y. Ablanazarov, M. Boltaboeva, A.Shirinov, U.Israilov, B.Ismatullaeva etc., winner of international and national competitions J.Idrisov, R.Alimardonov, R.Mirzakamolov, J.Orifjonov, Sh.Nurmatova, O.Nazirov, S.Jumaev, Zuhra and Fatima Tursunboevalar, L. Zakirova, S. Yigitaliev, B. Kamoliddinov, A. Usmonov, F.Ismatov, A.Akhmedova, S.Shermanov, O.Murodov, F.Embergenov, M.Akmaljonova, Kh.Sodigova and many worthy students are achieving high goals

without their teachers. In this place, professors-teachers of the department of "Academic Singing and Opera Preparation" of the State Conservatory of Uzbekistan, in the field of academic singing, conduct master-student lessons and master classes with experts in the field of opera, who are living and creating in different countries and who are engaged in scientific research. This opens the way for many new projects and concert activities, while bringing artists closer to each other through the art of opera.

Since singing, vocal, and opera arts occupy a special place in the life of our people today, their sounds are heard in radio and television, theater and concert halls, and schools.

Therefore, on August 27, 1996, the first President Islam Karimov issued a decree on the song holiday "Uzbekistan - My Motherland". According to this decree, on November 18, the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan decided to hold a traditional song festival. The decision states that: ". . . Musical works of a high artistic level, which glorify our working people, nurture the feelings of preserving the sacred soil of the Motherland and independence in the hearts of people, should be held as a song festival. . ." was defined as

In this place, our country organizes a number of contests and festivals in order to discover young talented singers, to raise a mature generation, and young opera singers take part in them. For example: It is a good thing that the "Spring of Youth" young opera singers audition-festival is organized and many young people participate and win in it.

Currently, there are vocal and academic singing departments in many music and art schools, music, art and pedagogical colleges, pedagogical universities, Tashkent State Institute of Culture named after Abdulla Qadiri, State Conservatory of Uzbekistan. Among these, with special attention, we can say that President Sh. Mirziyoev decided to establish a "Boarding school specialized in opera art" in Nukus, Republic of Karakalpakstan in 2021, as a high recognition of vocal art, especially academic singing. Of course, we hope that the art of opera can be a serious basis for awakening the minds of the young generation, educating aesthetic feelings, and introducing them to the world of beauty.

As a continuation of the above-mentioned ideas, on December 27, 2021, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyoyev signed the decision "On measures for the further development of the art of opera and ballet". serves to open wide doors of opportunity for the coming representatives, industry workers.

In our free and prosperous land, every young person, no matter what profession he chooses later, should learn and be well versed in the art of music. Of course, the role of theater art is incomparable in this. Theater is a means of elevating human spirituality, reaching the depths of emotions, understanding the experiences of the characters created in it, drawing appropriate conclusions from the work. There are works that give life a more solemn spirit, serve to beautify, enrich and improve. This is an opera. In addition to the embodiment of various art fields, operas reflect people's life, its reality and problems, and its heroes, and it constantly has its fans. It is gratifying that in recent years, newly created and restored Uzbek and world classical opera works are being performed in new interpretations on big stages, including the DAKT stage named after A. Navoi. Such works enrich the inner world of people and invite their life to beauty.

The above mentioned points are a sign of high attention and recognition of opera art in our country, which indicates that this field is developing, and in the future there is great hope for many new examples of creativity, young opera singers, bright names, new operas, new milestones will be reached at competitions and festivals.

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